

RAMONES

Radioactivity Monitoring in Ocean Ecosystems

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Disclaimer

RAMONES is a European Innovation Council (EIC) FET Proactive project in the Environmental Intelligence Scope B, related to radically novel approaches to resilient, reliable and environmentally responsible in-situ monitoring, funded by European Union under Horizon 2020 FET proactive programme, via grant agreement No. 101017808.

RAMONES project's main objective is to close the current marine radioactivity under-sampling gap and foster new interdisciplinary research in ocean ecosystems. RAMONES will invest a significant effort to provide tools to enable long-term data acquisition missions, rapid deployments, low cost per information byte, and propose new AI and Robotics-driven and supported methodologies, being ambitious to eventually offer scaled-up solutions to researchers, policy makers and communities. All these may be achieved by combining state-of-the-art (SoA) methodologies and equipment from various disciplines in a well-balanced synergy, and designing new and effective methodologies targeting the marine environment, which will provide efficient response to existing natural and man-made hazards, and shape future policies for the global population. RAMONES will additionally contribute to shaping a blueprint on Environmental Intelligence in the EU and worldwide.

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
EIC	European Innovation Council
EU	European Union
GA	Google Analytics
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
SoA	State of the Art
URL	Universal Resource Locator
WP	Work Package
WWW	World Wide Web

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Abstract

In the present deliverable D5.17, following the original plan deployed in D5.9 (Raise Awareness, Communication, Dissemination, Outreach, Engagement & Exploitation Plan), and the reports D5.12 (no3 - M36) and D5.13 (no4 - M48) on “Dissemination and Communication Activities”, we report separately the second report on “Outreach and Liaison Activities”.. We define clearly outreach and liaison activities as those activities that do not disseminate directly academic and scientific findings of the project (as these are presented separately in D5.10/D5.11/D5.12/D5.13) rather than mainly raise awareness of the implications and the impact of our project through wide-range events appealing to broader audiences, as well as direct liaisons with other projects of similar quests, including the ones from the same Call (i-Seed, SmartLagoon, ReSET, WatchPlant) that we share common deliverables in the Environmental Intelligence front (D5.19 on M12, D5.20 on M24, D5.21 on M36 and D5.22 on M48). The present document D5.17 covers the second half of the project (M25-M48).

1. Outreach

We start this report by listing outreach activities during the second half (M25 - M48) of the RAMONES projects, in chronological order:

- RAMONES members Angelos Mallios (PLOATECH) and Emanuele Coccolo (EVOLOGICS) participated in the Oceanology International in London on March 11th-14th, 2024.
- RAMONES project was presented in A&R Expo, the first Automation & Robotics Expo in Greece, which was held in the Athens Metropolitan Expo Center, between 12-14 April 2024. More details on this event will be presented in Section 3.2.

Figure 1 - Dr. Makis Ntouskos presenting the RAMONES project during the expo

- A RAMONES webinar took place on May 3rd, 2023 on “Autonomous Marine Robotics for Collaborative Radioactivity Mapping” that was led by Dr. David Cabecinhas (IST-ID, Lisbon) who presented the work that has been done in the WP2 of our project

Figure 2 - The lead screen of the webinar by Dr. David Cabecinhas

- A RAMONES seminar took place on 26th of May 2023 on “RAMONES and Environmental Intelligence: the way forward” by Prof. Kostas Nikolopoulos (UDUR) at Universite Clermont Auvergne (host: Prof. Lydia Maigne)

Figure 3 - The lead screen of the presentation of Prof. Kostas Nikolopoulos

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- The 1st Primary School of Papagou Lecture visited the Nuclear Physics laboratory of NKUA on May 29th, 2023. Lecture and training in radioactivity measurements using portable monitors and natural samples.

Figure 4 - Students at NKUA, Department of Physics

- The RAMONES team was active during the 87th and 88th International Fair of Thessaloniki which took place on September 15th-17th, 2023 and September 7th-15th, 2024, respectively. The Fair is the major international expo event in Greece attracting thousands of visitors annually. More details on this event will be presented in Section 3.2.

Figure 5 - WP6 Leader, Ms Eleni Petra, showcasing the RAMONES project during the 88th International Fair of Thessaloniki

- RAMONES project members participated actively in the Researcher's Night organized at the premises of the National Technical University of Athens on September 29th, 2023. More details on this event are presented in Section 2.2.
- Mr. Siltzovalis presented to the students of the "Medical Physics" Group of the 1st Lyceum of Costeas-Geitonas on November 1st, 2023, part of his PhD thesis, which is being carried out under the auspices of the RAMONES project.

Figure 6 – PhD candidate George Siltzovalis talk to students

- RAMONES team showcased RAMONES instruments to 50 high-school students at Santorini, on October 24th, 2024 giving them the opportunity to watch the team during action and receive important knowledge for the solutions offered via novel technology and methods.
- RAMONES project and equipment were presented to community stakeholders of Santorini Island on October 24th, 2024.
- In Feb 2024, the RAMONES Project was presented to the Radioactive Substances Commission of the OSPAR Convention (Lisbon, 6-9 Feb), as part of the NODSSUM Project to study radioactive waste in the deep ocean (June-July 2025).

2. Events and Activities

RAMONES has been active in various events and joint venture activities targeting citizen awareness and dissemination of the project. Most of the activities have been carried out mainly through digital channels.

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All of them have been reported on the RAMONES website (considering the goals, the challenges, the work carried out and the results) and disseminated through the RAMONES digital channels.

2.1. Conferences & workshops RAMONES (co)-organized or participated in

The most relevant workshops and conferences participated or (co)organized by the RAMONES team, reported and disseminated through all RAMONES digital channels during this period. They are briefly listed below, since they have been also reported in detail in the deliverable D5.13 (M48).

Table 1 - Workshops and conferences participated by RAMONES

Event Name	Type of event	RAMONES role	Place & Date
2nd RAMONES Workshop	Workshop	organisation	Athens, Greece, 17-18/01/2024
Industry CoP - Community Building Session	Workshop	presentation	EIC, 21/02/2024
MARTECH - The 11th International Workshop on Marine Technology	Workshop	presentation	University of Balearic Islands, Mallorca, Spain, 06-07/06/2024
RAP 2024	Conference	presentation	Granada, Spain, 10-12/06/2024
IUGC2024 - International Underwater Glider Conference 2024	Conference	presentation	Reveljen, Gothenburg, Sweden, 10-14/06/2024
IEEE IGARSS - International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium 2024	Conference	presentation	Megaron, Athens, Greece, 07-12/07/2024
International Conference of Applied Nuclear Physics	Conference	presentation	Thessaloniki, Greece, 23-27/09/2024
NTUAREN European Researchers Night	Public Event	presentation	Athens, Greece, 27/09/2024
6th International Conference on Radioecology & Environmental Radioactivity ICRER 2024	Conference	presentation	Marseille, France, 24-29/11/2024

Event Name	Type of event	RAMONES role	Place & Date
Exploring the Blue Frontier with Cooperative Marine Robots, CSIE Workshop, Innovations in Autonomous Systems	Workshop	presentation	Terevan, Armenia, 6/10/2024
Applications of Marine Robotics to Science and Ocean Literacy, VIII Workshop Sea and Atmosphere	Workshop	presentation	Univ. Aveiro, Portugal, 28/2/2024
Cooperative Marine Robotics, a 2 day course for MSc students	Course	presentation	Univ. Toulon, France, 21-22/5/2024
Encontro de Oceanografia 2024 [Oceanography Meeting] https://ciencias.ulisboa.pt/pt/evento/03-05-2024/encontro-de-oceanografia-2024	Conference	presentation	Peniche, Portugal, 3-4/5/2024
EMRA 2024 - Workshop on EU-funded Marine Robotics and Applications https://emra-24.marinerobotics.eu	Workshop	presentation	Arenzano, Italy, 27-29/5/2024

2.2. Fairs and exhibitions participated

RAMONES as has been mentioned above actively participated in the following events during the second half of the project:

1. A&R Expo (12-14 April 2024)

RAMONES project was presented in the first Automation & Robotics Expo in Greece, which brought together key stakeholders in the research and industry to showcase the latest advancements and technology in the field of automation and robotics. A&R Expo welcomed more than 7.500 visitors who had the chance to discuss in person with more than 120 exhibitors from Greece and all over the world.

The NTUA booth, where RAMONES was represented, has attracted a lot of visitors who had the opportunity to see a RAMONES autonomous underwater glider vehicle that has been customized to meet the goals of the project. RAMONES was successfully presented in the event, raising public awareness in the Greek audience regarding the project's challenges and outcomes. Moreover, our team member Dr. Valsamis Ntouskos (NTUA) gave a talk during the

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expo, under the title “AI for Intelligent Sensing and Analysis of Underwater Environments” where he presented RAMONES and explained the role of the autonomous robotic vehicles in the project.

2. 87th International Fair of Thessaloniki (15-17/9/2023)

WP6 Leader, Ms Eleni Petra, represented RAMONES in the largest and most important Expo Event in Greece. RAMONES’ stand attracted lots of visitors already from the very first day of the Fair, where they had the opportunity to get informed about the innovative solutions and technological advances RAMONES will bring along.

3. Researchers Night 2023 (29/9/2023)

RAMONES partners presented an overview of the project and its objectives to the general public in the Researchers Night Open Event in Greece held in the premises of the National Technical University of Athens mentioned also above. In the specific yearly event, scientists from various scientific fields discuss with children and young scientists about different scientific topics and multiple technological innovations promoting citizen awareness.

4. 88th International Fair of Thessaloniki (07-15/9/2024)

RAMONES WP6 Leader Eleni Petra presented the project’s scientific objectives and achievements to a large number of people participating in the expo. Moreover, our representative joined the workshop “The prospect and challenge of new small nuclear reactors on land and at sea” presented by the Greek Atomic Energy Commission.

3. Liaison

Hereafter we list the project switch which formal liaisons has been established and maintained throughout the RAMONES project:

3.1. Liaison with H2020 projects from the same FET call

- Liaised with the i-Seed project
- Liaised with the SmartLagoon project
- Liaised with the ReSET project
- Liaised with the WatchPlant project

With the above four projects, RAMONES has co-organized and participated in joint sessions during the two GoodIT conferences in 2021 and 2022, while common deliverables in the Environmental Intelligence front (5.19/5.20/5.21/5.22) have been prepared and submitted jointly. The 5 projects collaborate throughout their timelines in shaping the new grounds of Environmental Intelligence in Europe, identifying synergies, strengthening their research potential, but also highlighting important steps required for open dissemination of their results to a broader scale. The joint deliverables contain several details, which are not included in the present manuscript to avoid repetition. In addition, several joint events and actions have been organized, in which the projects participated with their partners, such as conferences, workshops or summer schools.

3.2. Liaison with H2020 projects

- Liaised with HORIZON EUROPE nexus-monARC with the first contact made on November 8th, 2023

The nexus monARC project proposes a set of capacity building actions targeting to advance the profile of staff at the department of geology and geoenvironment and collaborating groups at the NKUA. Through these actions, a holistic approach to environmental monitoring will be developed for the marine environment of the Hellenic Volcanic Arc in the Mediterranean Sea, an environment that is influenced by multiple stressors of anthropogenic and natural origin. The project objectives will be achieved through transferring knowledge and best practices based on the extensive

expertise of partner institutions and by orchestrating citizen science activities. Short scientific missions synchronized to citizen science activities will lead to the development of novel collaborative research projects for the coordinating and partner institutions. Furthermore, twinning activities will incite local and international stakeholders from public, policy, and industry to participate and contribute to educational and scientific actions, thus actively improving the marine environment and protecting its inhabitants. RAMONES and nexus-monARC have co-signed an MoU to explore synergies and collaboration, especially in the domain of underwater research.

- Liaised with H2020 PSLifestyle

PSLifestyle (*Co-Creating a Positive and Sustainable Lifestyle tool with and for European Residents*; <https://pslifestyle.eu/>) is an EU-funded project which aims to close the gap between climate awareness and individual action. RAMONES has liaised with the project, exploring further collaboration in the broader framework of environmental intelligence, supporting also some of the core actions of PSLifestyle (e.g. filling questionnaires and promoting their objectives through the RAMONES website and network email list).

3.3. Liaison with other projects

- Liaised with NODSSUM project (France) to study radioactive waste disposal sites in the deep sea (North-East Atlantic).

The NODSSUM Project targets the dump site of radioactive waste in the North-East Atlantic. This site is located at abyssal plains (3000-5000 m), and hosts >200000 barrels of low- and medim- activity waste, dumped in the 40's to 80's. After an initial study of the site in the 80's, that revealed low levels of radionuclides linked to this waste, no study has been conducted since. The NODSSUM project will conduct two oceanographic cruises, operated by the French Oceanographic Fleet. A first cruise will deploy an autonomous vehicle and instrumentation in June-July 2025. A second cruise will be conducted in 2026 or 2027 (dates to be confirmed). RAMONES is in liaison with this cruise program, to explore the possibility of deploying instrumentation to monitor radioactivity at this site. This will require the adaptation of RAMONES instrumentation for deep-ocean conditions (>1000 m water depth).